

SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF TABOOS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

Taboos play an important role in language use and the formation of cultural norms. This article aims to conduct a semantic analysis of taboos in English and Uzbek languages. By studying the linguistic markings, cultural influences, and pragmatic aspects of taboo topics in these languages, we seek to uncover the underlying semantic structures and social norms associated with taboo topics.

Taboos are embedded in every society and serve as markers of what is socially or culturally forbidden, inappropriate, or sacred. These restrictions on language and behavior play a crucial role in defining societal norms and values. By studying the semantic aspects of taboos in English and Uzbek, we can gain valuable information about how linguistic expressions, cultural beliefs, and social practices intersect and influence each other, reflected in phrases and topics. These linguistic restrictions not only shape the forms of communication, but also reveal deep social attitudes towards certain subjects. By conducting a semantic analysis of taboos in English and Uzbek, we aim to study the main structures of taboo language and their cultural consequences. Language is not only a means of communication, but also a reflection of cultural values and norms. Taboos are evidence of the symbiotic relationship between language and culture, highlighting the ways in which language is used to reinforce social boundaries and uphold cultural traditions. By carefully examining taboo language in English and Uzbek, we can identify unique semantic cues, pragmatic considerations, and communicative strategies used to navigate taboo topics in these language contexts.¹

At its core, a taboo is a social prohibition or restriction that dictates what is considered unacceptable, impure, or sacred within a given society. These taboos can encompass a wide range of behaviors, actions, and objects, from specific dietary restrictions to certain forms of speech or expression. The semantic analysis of taboos reveals the underlying reasons and justifications for their existence, shedding light on the cultural, religious, moral, or historical factors that contribute to their reinforcement and perpetuation. One common semantic

¹ Abdullayev A. Expressive feature of phraseologisms. - T.: EXTREME. 1976. No. 5.

feature of taboos is their association with notions of purity and pollution. For example, in many cultures, certain foods are considered taboo due to their perceived impurity or contamination. In Hinduism, the consumption of beef is taboo for adherents of the faith, as cows are revered as sacred animals. This taboo reflects a deeply held belief in the sanctity of life and the importance of respecting all forms of existence.

Furthermore, by comparing and contrasting taboo language across different cultural and linguistic frameworks, we can reveal key universals and idiosyncratic features that define the boundaries of acceptable speech in English and Uzbek societies. This comparative analysis sheds light on the ways in which taboos are negotiated, managed, and challenged through language, and ultimately contributes to a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between language, culture, and societal norms let's get acquainted with the methodology, findings and consequences. By examining the semantic structures, communicative functions, and cultural nuances of taboo language, we aim to offer a nuanced perspective on the role of taboos in language use, identity formation, and intercultural communication in different linguistic contexts.²

Taboos are social or cultural restrictions on certain topics, behaviors, or expressions that are considered inappropriate, forbidden, or sacred in a particular society. These taboos are often reflected in the use of language, manifested in certain vocabulary, expressions and communicative strategies. By conducting a semantic analysis of taboos in English and Uzbek, we aim to deepen our understanding of how these linguistic constraints shape communication and reflect cultural values. This research methodology includes a combination of lexical analysis, pragmatic analysis, cultural semantics, and comparative analysis takes We look at forbidden words, phrases and topics in English and Uzbek languages, analyze their semantic meanings, social significance and communicative functions. By comparing and contrasting the semantic features of taboos in these two languages, we aim to identify commonalities, differences, and idiosyncrasies that illuminate the cultural and linguistic contexts of taboo language use.³

Through our semantic analysis, we expect to reveal the ways in which taboos are linguistically encoded, perceived, and manipulated in English and Uzbek. We expect to identify taboo markers, semantic nuances, and pragmatic considerations that influence the communication of taboo topics in these linguistic contexts. By examining cultural sensitivities and social norms related to taboos, we aim to provide insight into how language reflects and reinforces social boundaries and values learns We consider the role of taboos in language use, identity formation, and cultural practices in English and Uzbek-speaking communities. By considering the broader implications of our semantic analysis, we aim to contribute to a deeper understanding of the complex relationship between language, culture, and taboo subjects.⁴

Conclusion. In conclusion, this article presents a comprehensive semantic analysis of taboos in the English and Uzbek languages, highlighting the complex interrelationship between language, culture and societal norms. By examining the semantic structures and communicative functions of taboo language, we aim to shed light on the cultural significance of taboo subjects and the ways in which they are transmitted through language. This research contributes to the broader discourse on language and culture by emphasizing the importance of understanding taboos in developing effective intercultural communication and linguistic awareness.

² Abdullayev A. Expression of expressiveness in the Uzbek language. - T.: Science. 1983.

³ Kharatova, S. K. (2021). TENDENCIES OF DEVELOPMENT OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN GLOBAL TRANSFORMATION. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(10), 353-362.

⁴ Mamatov A.E. "Formation of Uzbek phraseology.-T.:1997.-B.37.

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